

Accurate object detection using the sensor fusion of an event-based and a frame-based camera

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Abstract

Efficient object detection is crucial to real-time monitoring applications such as autonomous driving. Modern RGB cameras can produce high-resolution images for accurate object detection. However, with increased resolution comes increased network latency and power consumption. To minimise this latency, CNNs often have a resolution limitation, requiring images to be down-sampled before inference, causing significant information loss. In this paper, we propose a neuromorphic vision approach based on biological vision, where images are cropped instead of down-sampled to meet the requirements of the CNN. The design implements the sensor fusion of an event-based camera and a frame-based RGB camera to implement an accurate, low-power monitoring system. The cameras are calibrated to create a multi-modal stereo vision system where pixel coordinates can be projected between the event camera and RGB camera image planes. Events are detected using clustering on the event-based data and projected to the RGB image plane using the calibration results. These projections identify important areas in the RGB image, directing the cropping areas. Using this implementation, the COCO AP is increased from 21.08 to 57.38 on bicycles in the RGB scene, with an overall increase from 37.93 to 46.89 for all classes tested.

Keywords: Sensor Fusion, Event-Based Vision, Camera Calibration, Object Detection, Image Processing

1 Introduction

Efficient monitoring systems are needed for a range of applications including autonomous vehicles, and security systems. Many of these applications are safety-critical systems that require high accuracy, and high temporal resolution to ensure that accurate responses are made in real-time. Modern cameras have improved significantly in recent years resulting in higher-quality images with improved resolution and dynamic range. Although this helps significantly with accurate object detection, it also comes at a cost. The power consumption and bandwidth needed to process these high-quality images are very high. Because of this, many convolutional neural networks (CNNs) have a resolution limitation to meet latency constraints. The resolution of images imputed into these networks is typically limited to 600x600 pixels or less, meaning that high-resolution images must be down-sampled, therefore reducing the accuracy of the detection, especially for smaller details in the image.

An event camera is a neuromorphic vision sensor, processing only the changes in a scene rather than the entire scene. In these sensors, each pixel asynchronously measures logarithmic changes in light intensity and records any changes that are above or below a pre-defined threshold. This removes a huge amount of redundant data which would be recorded in a regular camera, where data is recorded by every pixel at a pre-defined interval, wasting power and memory on static, unchanging scenes [Prophasee, 2023]. The resulting data recorded by these cameras is a sequence of events corresponding to areas of movement in the image in the form of the x , y coordinates of the pixel, the time, and the polarity of the light intensity change (increasing or decreasing brightness).

This design provides many advantages over state-of-the-art frame-based cameras. Event cameras can achieve temporal resolutions $> 10,000$ fps (frames per second), with sub-millisecond latency. Also, the dynamic range achievable by event cameras is >120 dB making the sensors more robust to adverse conditions such as low light, or glare from the sun.

In this work, we propose an object detection system using the sensor fusion of an event-based camera with a frame-based camera. The design takes inspiration from the human visual system. The event camera acts as the low-resolution peripheral vision to detect movement in the scene, while the RGB camera acts as the fovea where high-resolution analysis of the image is completed. During this analysis, the RGB images will be cropped instead of down-sampled to meet the resolution limitations of the CNN used, allowing high-accuracy detection without forfeiting temporal resolution.

The main contributions of this research include: an adaptation to common camera calibration techniques which facilitates the calibration of an event-based camera with a frame-based camera using common automated software; a simple equation that can be used to project pixel coordinates from the image plane of one camera to the other with reasonable accuracy, when complex geometrical analysis is not feasible; a foveal vision approach to real-time object detection using an event camera to reduce information loss in high-resolution RGB images, showing considerable accuracy improvements for small objects.

Figure 1: Example frame from the event camera (left) and RGB camera (right).

2 State of the Art

2.1 Event-based vision

Numerous recent studies investigate the use of event cameras for object detection and tracking. Rebecq et al propose a recurrent neural network, which can be used to reconstruct high-resolution grayscale images from event streams [Rebecq et al., 2019]. The results show impressive quality and give good classification accuracy on off-the-shelf CNNs; however, this comes at an increased computational cost. Shariff et al demonstrated a proof of concept forward perception system using event-based YOLOv5 detection [Shariff et al., 2023]. The viability of raw event data in object detection models is shown by [Perot et al., 2020] and [Ryan et al., 2021], but the training of such models is limited by the availability of event-based training data, with [Ryan et al., 2021] using a simulated dataset for training. The use of unsupervised clustering algorithms combats this issue for tracking moving objects [Hinz et al., 2017, Mondal et al., 2021, Mondal and Das, 2021], but these algorithms do not provide sufficient information for object classification. In this work, the combination of data from an event-based camera and a frame-based camera allows common frame-based object detection techniques to be implemented and advanced using the characteristics of the event camera.

2.2 Sensor Fusion

There is a significant amount of research exploring the sensor fusion of RADAR (Radio Detection and Ranging) or LiDAR (Light Detection and Ranging) with regular cameras to gather depth information in a scene [Willis et al., 2009, Chai et al., 2018, Zhou et al., 2018, Kim and Park, 2019, Singandhupe and La, 2021], yet there is limited research on the multi-modal fusion of event-based cameras. The idea of combining event-based sensors with regular frame-based sensors is investigated for object detection [Perot et al., 2020, Tomy et al., 2022],

SLAM [Weikersdorfer et al., 2013, Vidal et al., 2018, Gao et al., 2022], optical flow estimation [Lee et al., 2022], and visual odometry [Chen et al., 2023]. The DAVIS sensor [Brandli et al., 2014] is used in many of the sensor fusion implementations [Zhu et al., 2018, Chen et al., 2023, Lee et al., 2022], which combines an asynchronous Dynamic Vision Sensor (DVS) with a synchronous frame-based sensor on a single photodiode. In this sensor, the event-based and frame-based cameras share a common reference frame making the calibration process easier, as standard calibration can be run on the frame-based image. Unfortunately, the low resolution of the sensor limits its functionality in object detection systems. Other approaches use stereo event camera systems in combination with high-resolution frame-based stereo systems to calculate depth in the 3D coordinate system [Vidal et al., 2018, Gehrig et al., 2021, Gao et al., 2022]. However, the implementation of a multi-modal stereo system where image points are projected between event-based and frame-based image planes of contrasting resolutions is limited to [Tomy et al., 2022]. Tomy et al show improvements in model robustness in adverse weather conditions using event-based data combined with frame-based data. However, the effects on the complexity of the resulting network are not evaluated. Each of these sensor fusion approaches involves data collection from both cameras simultaneously, and the event data is combined with each regular frame to evaluate the results. This increases the complexity of the system and does not take advantage of the low power consumption available with event cameras.

3 Methodology

3.1 Data

The data was collected by a camera rig containing an event camera and an RGB camera, highlighted in Table 1. A thirty-second video sample is used for testing, which consists of vehicles, bikes, and pedestrians maneuvering around Dangan Car Park, Galway. An example frame from each camera is seen in Figure 1. The RGB data was recorded at a frame rate of 30 fps, giving an accumulation time of 33,333 μ s. This accumulation time is used to generate and visualise frames from the event data, which could be synchronised with the RGB video.

3.1.1 Camera Calibration

In this study, a modified version of the method proposed by [Zhang, 2000] was used. The static checkerboard was replaced with a flashing checkerboard GIF (Graphics Interchange Format), and by displaying it on a large LCD screen, images can be gener-

	Event Camera	RGB Camera
Name	PROPHASEE ONBOARD	Blackfly S
Spatial Resolution (pixels)	640 x 480	4096 x 2160
Temporal Resolution (fps)	>5000	42
Dynamic Range (dB)	>120	<50
Power Consumption (W)	0.026	3
Pixel Pitch (μ m)	15	3.45

Table 1: Specifications of cameras used in the dataset.

ated from the event-based and frame-based cameras allowing stereo calibration using standard toolboxes. In this research, the Stereo Camera Calibrator App available from the MATLAB Computer Vision Toolbox is used to calculate the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of each camera according to the following steps: create a flashing checkerboard GIF and display on a large screen; mount RGB camera on apparatus beside event camera and ensure apparatus is stable and secure; record video of flashing checkerboard using both cameras simultaneously and repeat for 10 – 20 different camera angles; generate event-based frames from event-camera data and extract corresponding frames from RGB video data; process images to ensure aspect ratios match and resize images to have the same resolution, by cropping the event frame to 640x338 pixels and downscaling the RGB image to this resolution; calibrate cameras using software to determine the intrinsic and extrinsic parameters of each camera.

Following successful calibration, Equation 1 can be used to project pixel coordinates from the event-camera frame, $[x_2, y_2]$, to the RGB camera frame, $[x_1, y_1]$. This equation uses the intrinsic parameters which remain

constant for each camera, K_1 , K_2 , and the extrinsic parameters, R_1 , R_2 , and t_1 , t_2 , which change depending on the location of each camera. The extrinsic parameters of the cameras were not recorded at the time of the dataset collection, so the parameters used in this equation are the average relative extrinsic parameters of the two cameras, $(R_E)_{av}$. This can be derived according to Equation 1 for each set of extrinsic parameters and finding the mean over all angles used in the calibration. By using this average extrinsic value, this equation can be generalised to any situation if the cameras remain in the same position relative to each other.

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_1 \\ x_2 \\ x_3 \end{bmatrix} = \frac{K_1}{K_2} \cdot (R_E)_{av} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} x_2 \\ y_2 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$R_E = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} R_1 & t_1 \\ R_2 & t_2 \end{bmatrix}}{\quad} \quad (2)$$

3.2 Clustering & Object Detection

To detect and track moving objects in the event-camera data, clustering can be used to group events into objects. To implement this, event coordinates are processed into an array for each frame according to the accumulation time of the RGB camera. Prior to implementing the clustering, the following steps are run on the resulting array: remove any out-of-frame points to account for the change in aspect ratio used in the calibration; undistort the points using the OpenCV `undistortPoints` function with the intrinsic matrix and distortion coefficients of the event camera.

The DBSCAN clustering algorithm is then run on the formatted array to determine the locations of each moving object in the event camera data. To determine their location in the RGB frame, Equation 1 is used to project the resulting bounding box coordinates to the RGB image plane. This equation assumes that the images used are the same resolution as the images used in the calibration process, and that lens distortion has been removed. To convert the resulting points to the original RGB image plane, the coordinates must be distorted using the distortion coefficients of the RGB camera, according to Equation 3, and converted back to the original RGB camera resolution using Equation 4. These bounding box coordinates can then be used to crop the RGB frame, and object detection is run on the cropped images.

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= (1 + 2p_1 + p_2(r^2 + 2x^2) + k_1r^2 + k_2r^4)x \\ y' &= (1 + 2p_2 + p_1(r^2 + 2y^2) + k_1r^2 + k_2r^4)y \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$x'' = \frac{4096x'}{640}, \quad y'' = \frac{2160y'}{338} \quad (4)$$

Where (x, y) are the projected points, (x', y') are the distorted points, and (x'', y'') are the points in the original RGB image. (k_1, k_2, p_1, p_2) are the distortion coefficients, and $r^2 = x^2 + y^2$. The object detection model used in this research is the YOLOv5s model [Jocker, 2020]. The resolution requirements for the model are for the input images to be 640x640 pixels. PyTorch is used for inference, and all required data augmentation is automatically completed on the image when inputted into the model.

3.3 Performance Evaluation

Performance is measured using mean average precision (mAP), which combines precision, recall, and bounding box accuracy using an intersection over union (IoU) threshold. The Microsoft COCO dataset [Lin et al., 2014] calculates the AP over a range of IoU thresholds. The standard COCO metric measures over ten thresholds from 0.5 – 0.95 with an increment of 0.05. The method used in the PASCAL VOC dataset [Everingham et al., 2010] calculates the average AP over each class for a fixed IoU threshold. AP50 uses a threshold of 50 %, while AP75 uses a threshold of 75 %. To investigate the advantages of the application, the performance of the system is compared against the baseline of running the same model on each full frame of the RGB video data.

4 Results & Discussion

The calibration accuracy is measured according to the reprojection error of the checkerboard corners for each calibration image. Table 2 shows the results achieved for the initial calibration, the final calibration, and from using Equation 1 to project the points. The original calibration gave the lowest mean reprojection error, however only 13 images were used, and the entire FOV of the cameras were not covered. When tested on real-world data, this calibration performed poorly at the edges of the image. More data was collected to cover a larger area of the FOV, and the calibration was repeated, giving an error of 0.24 pixels. Figure 2 shows accurate reprojection by the MATLAB software for a calibration image at the edge of the image, validating the calibration.

Figure 2: Reprojection results using MATLAB Stereo Camera Calibrator

Using these calibration results, Equation 1 was used to project corners from the event camera image to the RGB camera image, giving a mean reprojection error of 1.42 pixels, according to Table 2. This does show an increased error; however, it is still only slightly over 1 pixel, and it allows the projection to be generalised and used on data where the exact extrinsic parameters of the camera are unknown.

Method	# Images	Mean Reprojection Error
MATLAB Original Calibration	13	0.09
MATLAB Original Calibration	17	0.24
Projection using Equation 1	17	1.42

Table 2: Reprojection error for two calibration attempts, and error calculated using derived equation with parameters from final calibration.

5 Clustering & Object Detection

Hyperparameter tuning of the DBSCAN clustering algorithm was performed through visual analysis. The hyperparameters chosen were Epsilon=20 and minPoints=10. The results of the DBSCAN algorithm and the projection of the resulting bounding boxes are shown for an example frame in Figure 3. Note that both images are undistorted in this figure.

Table 3 shows the results achieved on the full-frame implementation (FF), and the cropped implementation (Crop) using the sensor fusion approach. The accuracy results achieved using COCO AP, AP50, and AP75 are highlighted. The results are calculated for each class, and an average over all classes is calculated. The % tab shows the factor of improvement of the cropped detection over the full-frame detection according to Equation 5.

Figure 3: Results of DBSCAN clustering to and projection to RGB image using Equation 1

$$\% = \frac{Crop - FF}{FF} \quad (5)$$

Looking at the results achieved using COCO AP, the cropped implementation shows an improvement factor of 0.24 over all classes. The bicycle class accuracy improves by a factor of 1.72 from 21 % to 57 %. The person class also shows an improvement of 0.32. The car class sees a decrease in accuracy from 47.54 % to 23.55 %. It is important to note the limitations of this metric for the car class. On initial measurement, the accuracy of the car class was very low, giving only 7.83 % and 5.35 % COCO AP for the full-frame and cropped implementations, respectively. This application is interested in moving objects only, therefore any static objects in the frame were not annotated in the dataset. Unfortunately, this resulted in the parked cars in the image being marked as false positives during the accuracy evaluation resulting in very low precision scores. To avoid this, the background was blurred using a median filter mask. This increased precision for both implementations. However, it increased recall for the full frame implementation, but decreased recall for the cropped implementation. For this reason, the accuracy results cannot be reliably compared for the car class.

	COCO AP			AP50			AP75		
	FF	Crop	%	FF	Crop	%	FF	Crop	%
Car	47.54	23.55	-0.5	55.62	34.05	-0.39	53.88	23.59	-0.56
Person	45.16	59.73	0.32	76.15	84.19	0.11	45.05	69.08	0.53
Bicycle	21.08	57.38	1.72	39.33	70.61	0.8	22.86	67.00	1.93
Average	37.93	46.89	0.24	57.03	62.95	0.1	40.60	53.22	0.31

Table 3: Object detection results for full-frame (FF) and cropped (Crop) implementations

A similar relationship can be seen in the AP50 and AP75 results, with the bicycle class showing the highest improvement, and the car class showing a decrease in accuracy. The accuracy of the full-frame implementation reduces when the IoU threshold is increased from 0.5 – 0.75. For the person, bicycle, and average classes, the improvement factor of the crop over the full frame increases significantly for AP75: from 0.11 to 0.53 for the person class; 0.8 to 1.93 for the bicycle class; and 0.1 to 0.31 overall. This shows that the bounding box prediction is more accurate when using the cropped images, as fewer predictions are eliminated by the increased threshold.

6 Conclusions & Future Work

In this research, an ‘Artificial Fovea’ is proposed using the sensor fusion of an event camera with an RGB camera. We outline a method of calibrating an event camera with an RGB camera using a standard calibration toolbox and an equation is derived to allow projection between image planes of each camera without additional extrinsic calibration. The design implements the DBSCAN clustering algorithm on event-based data to determine the location of moving objects in a scene. These results are projected to the RGB camera image plane using the derived equation. The RGB frame is then cropped according to these results, and object detection is run on each of these cropped images. The system is evaluated by measuring the accuracy of the object detection achieved using the YOLOv5s algorithm and comparing these results with the same model run on each full frame of data from the RGB video. The cropping of the images shows good accuracy improvements over the full frame implementation with the COCO AP increasing from 37.93 % for the full frame implementation, to 46.89 % on the cropped frames. The highest accuracy improvement was seen for the bicycle class where the COCO AP increased from 21.08 % to 57.38 %. This shows the advantages of cropping the frame before inference, particularly for small objects in the image. This work highlights the accuracy improvements that can be achieved. Further analysis is required to address the low AP scores for the car class. It is likely, however, that the poor AP scores for the car class are due to data labeling issues and handling of static objects, rather than an intrinsic limitation of the proposed approach. Future work will explore the potential benefits of the proposed approach, including potential improvements in object detection accuracy, power consumption, frame rate, and image compression.

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